

DEADLINE-AWARE COMPUTATION OFFLOADING METHOD FOR DEPENDENT TASKS IN MEC-ENABLED NETWORKS

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Abstract. Finding optimal offloading decisions for dependent tasks with multiple objectives and hard deadlines in resource-constrained mobile edge computing networks is a challenging problem. The solution to this problem is essential for latency-sensitive real-time applications. The objective of the problem is to complete the task within the deadline while minimizing energy consumption on the smart mobile device. We propose a combination of the fuzzy logic technique and the NSGA-III algorithm to solve the problem. Experimental results show that the proposed method outperforms the random and MOPSO-based methods.

Keywords: mobile edge computing, optimal computation offloading, fuzzy logic.

Introduction. Developing the electronics industry and network technologies allows software developers to create new applications. On the other hand, the software developers put pressure on devices and network channels by raising the requirements. The applications, such as smart health, online games, smart glasses, etc., require ultra-low latency. The computation power of smart mobile devices (SMDs) is not always enough to process the tasks generated by the aforementioned applications within given time. Offloading the tasks on cloud resources may be a solution; however, this causes a longer delay due to the long distance between the data source and cloud servers. From this aspect, mobile edge computing (MEC) offers a short delay in transmitting data by allocating resources nearby data source. Conversely, the MEC has limited computation resources. There are several works that propose solutions to this problem. Our study on recent works in this field shows that reducing the latency, energy consumption of SMDs, and task failure remains a challenging problem. Because, most of studies have ignored gaining tasks in a queue caused by computation and computing capacity limitations of SMDs, wireless channels, or edge nodes. The applications that generate dependent tasks with hard-deadline constraints raise the complexity of the problem. To solve this problem, we propose a hybrid computation offloading optimization method. In this method, first, the subtasks are offloaded according to their task parameters and the states of SMD utilization, edge node computing unit, and

wireless channel. In this step, fuzzy logic with expert opinions is used to make offloading decisions. As a result, the subtask is assigned a more appropriate location for execution. Second, the subtasks that do not match the fuzzy rules are offloaded using the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-III).

The advantage of this method is that these two algorithms complement each other. Covering all possible combinations of fuzzy rules raises the time complexity of the fuzzy logic algorithm. On the other hand, the NSGA-III algorithm creates an initial random population. Next, the fittest chromosome is sought throughout the population. A larger population size increases the likelihood of finding the fittest chromosomes. However, searching for them is time-consuming. Fuzzy logic helps find the fittest chromosome during the creation of an initial population. Herewith, it is not required full set of fuzzy rules. Thus, we get an efficient way of computation offloading (CO).

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- A CO optimization method is proposed for deadline-constrained task flow with dependent subtasks.
- The proposed method was evaluated with simulation experiments comparing it to existing methods.
- The results of the evaluation show that the proposed method performs better in the given case.

Related works. In [1-3], authors proposed CO methods for cases where tasks are dependent. Their objectives are to minimize latency and energy consumption to improve the quality of service. In [4], the authors proposed a collaborative offloading method, where tasks might be offloaded either to a cloud server or an edge node. The decision is made using fuzzy logic based on server capacity, latency sensitivity, and the network’s state. The advantage of this work is supporting both horizontal (among MEC nodes) and vertical (MEC node and cloud server) offloading. Sonmez et al. [5] solved the orchestration problem in the edge cloud systems to improve the performance in terms of service time, failed tasks, and virtual machine (VM) virtualization. Their concern is where to execute already offloaded tasks, either on an edge node or a cloud server. The fuzzy logic decision is made based on input parameters such as bandwidth, transferred data size, CPU speed, and delay sensitivity. The authors selected triangular form of membership function in a fuzzy inference system. Also, Khanh et al. [6] proposed the fuzzy logic workload balancing method to improve the quality of service of the real-time applications. The proposed method was evaluated compared to the benchmark methods in terms of service time, task failure, and processing time. Their method consists of two stages: first, making a decision whether to execute a task either on a local edge node or a remote edge node using input parameters such as MAN delay, local edge VM utilization, and remote edge VM virtualization. In the second stage, a decision is made to execute either on the neighbour edge node or cloud server using four input parameters, such as WAN bandwidth, length of incoming task, edge node VM utilization, and delay sensitivity. These works are intended for latency-sensitive applications; however, there is no set deadline for task completion. Also, the aforementioned works for cases where tasks are independent.

Song et al. [7] propose a decentralized Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method for deadline-aware tasks to reduce communications costs between edge nodes. However, they did not consider energy consumption. Azizi et al. [8] examined the energy

consumption of fog nodes and task deadlines. They solved the problem in two steps. First, it optimizes task scheduling to meet deadline requirements, then minimizes energy consumption and the number of deadline violations.

In this work, the author proposes a CO method for MEC-enabled SMDs to minimize latency, energy consumption, and task failure caused by limited resources and deadline constraints. Also, minimizing deadline violations is taken into account. Table 1 presents a comparison between this work and recent similar research.

Table 1: Comparison of the proposed method to similar works.

Ref.	Contributions	Latency	Energy consumption	Task failure	Task dependency	Deadline-aware
[1]	A method for dynamic selection of edge cloud for offloading tasks	+	+	-	+	+
[2]	A model-free approach based on reinforcement learning	+	+	-	+	-
[3]	A multi-objective evolutionary approach (NSGA-III)	+	+	-	-	-
[4]	A fuzzy logic-based collaborative offloading method	+	-	+	-	-
[5]	A fuzzy logic-based orchestration system	+	-	-	-	-
[6]	A fuzzy logic-based workload balancing method	+	-	+	-	-

[7]	DRL-based decentralized CO method	+	-	+	+	+
[8]	Semi-greedy based task scheduling method	+	+		-	+
This work	A fuzzy logic-based hybrid method using the NSGA-III algorithm	+	+	+	+	+

System Model and Problem Formulation

Suppose there is a system consisting of an MEC node, a set of SMDs, and several small cells. The application running on the SMD generates N tasks that are compound, i.e., each task contains k_n dependent subtasks. The dependencies among subtasks are given by a directed acyclic graph (DAG) $G = (\tau_{m,n,k}, \rho)$, where $\tau_{m,n,k}$ denotes a subtask and ρ denotes the precedence constraint between tasks i and k . Any subtasks might be executed either on SMD or the MEC node, except for the first and the last ones. Because a task is generated at SMD, and its final result is shown at SMD. Each subtask $\tau_{m,n,k}$ is given by two parameters $(d_{m,n,k}, c_{m,n,k})$, where $d_{m,n,k}$ denotes the data size (DS) of the subtask and $c_{m,n,k}$ denotes the number of required CPU cycles (NRCC) to complete the subtask. We assume the values of DS and NRCC follow the exponential distribution.

An example of compound tasks with dependent subtasks is given in Fig. 1. Tasks must be completed within the time deadline θ_m ; otherwise, the task is failed.

The computation and communication models are adopted from [9]. The average task completion time is calculated as:

$$T = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N T_{m,n,k_n} \quad (1)$$

where T_{m,n,k_n} the completion time of the k_n subtask is the completion time of a task.

The average energy consumption of tasks of all SMDs is calculated as

$$E = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^{k_n} E_{m,n,k} \quad (2)$$

In this work, we consider the probability of task failure caused by exceeding the deadline. It is calculated as follows

$$\pi_m^{dv} = \begin{cases} 0, & T_{m,n,k_n} \leq \theta_{m,n} \\ \frac{k_n}{\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N k_n}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: An example of task flow with dependent subtasks.

Next, the value of the probability of task failure in the whole system is calculated by the three steps. First, find the probability of task failure in each SMD by adding the probabilities of task failure during local execution (π^l), transmission through the wireless channel (π^{tr}), and deadline violation (π^{dv}) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_1 &= \pi_1^l + \pi_1^{tr} + \pi_1^{dv} - \pi_1^l \pi_1^{tr} - \pi_1^l \pi_1^{dv} - \pi_1^{tr} \pi_1^{dv} \\ &\quad + \pi_1^l \pi_1^{tr} \pi_1^{dv} \\ \pi_2 &= \pi_2^l + \pi_2^{tr} + \pi_2^{dv} - \pi_2^l \pi_2^{tr} - \pi_2^l \pi_2^{dv} - \pi_2^{tr} \pi_2^{dv} \\ &\quad + \pi_2^l \pi_2^{tr} \pi_2^{dv} \\ \pi_3 &= \pi_3^l + \pi_3^{tr} + \pi_3^{dv} - \pi_3^l \pi_3^{tr} - \pi_3^l \pi_3^{dv} - \\ &\quad \pi_3^{tr} \pi_3^{dv} + \pi_3^l \pi_3^{tr} \pi_3^{dv} \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

$$\pi_M = \pi_M^l + \pi_M^{tr} + \pi_M^{dv} - \pi_M^l \pi_M^{tr} - \pi_M^l \pi_M^{dv} - \pi_M^{tr} \pi_M^{dv} - \pi_M^l \pi_M^{tr} \pi_M^{dv} \quad (4)$$

Second, the probabilities of task failure in M SMDs are calculated by adding the probabilities of task failure in each SMD using the equation for the extension of the addition theorem of probability to M events, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{SMDs} &= \sum_{m=1}^M \pi_m - \sum \sum \pi_m \pi_{j_{1 \leq m < j \leq M}} + \\ &\quad + \sum \sum \sum \pi_m \pi_j \pi_k_{1 \leq m < j < k \leq M} + \dots + \\ &\quad (-1)^{M-1} \pi_1 \pi_2 \pi_3 \dots \pi_M \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Third, the overall probability of task failure is computed by adding the probabilities of task failure on the edge node and M SMDs as follows

$$\Pi = \pi_e + \pi_{SMDs} - \pi_e \pi_{SMDs} \quad (6)$$

A constrained multi-objective optimization problem is formulated to find the best CO decisions that will minimize the energy used by SMDs, the average time it takes to finish a task, and the probability that the task will fail:

$$P1: \quad \min_{x_{m,n,k}} \{T, E, \Pi\} \quad (7)$$

s.t.

$$C1: T_{m,n,k_n} \leq \theta_{m,n}$$

$$C2: x_{m,n,k} \in \{0,1\}, \quad \{k \in Z: 2 \leq k \leq k_n - 1\}$$

$$C3: x_{m,n,k} = 0, \quad k \in \{1, k_n\}$$

$$C4: T_{m,n,k_n} \geq T_{m,n,z}, \quad z \in \mathbf{pred}(k)$$

According to the system model, there is a requirement to select a solution where the strict deadline is met. Thus, a constraint $C1$ defines that the completion time of each task cannot exceed the deadline given by an application. The constraint $C2$ defines that the offloading decision is binary. The constraint $C3$ defines that optimal offloading decisions are sought for subtasks from the second to the ninth in each task. The first and tenth subtasks are executed locally. The constraint $C4$ shows that the subtask $\tau_{m,n,k}$ cannot be finished before its predecessor.

A Fuzzy Logic-based Hybrid Offloading Method

In this section, we introduce a hybrid method that is based on the combination of fuzzy logic and NSGA-III algorithms.

Fuzzy Logic-based offloading decisions. Zadeh [10] introduced fuzzy set theory. Fuzzy logic is an effective tool to design intelligent systems and has been successfully applied to the financial, scientific, and engineering disciplines of decision-support systems, control problems, pattern recognition, modeling, and prediction. Moreover, in the last few years, there has been a rapid growth of applications using fuzzy logic. The proposed idea uses set membership as the key to decision-making when faced with uncertainty [11]. The point of fuzzy logic is to map an input space to an output space, and the primary

mechanism for doing this is a list of if-then statements called rules. All rules are evaluated in parallel, and the order of the rules is not significant. Fuzzy logic is all about the relative importance of precision.

A Fuzzy Logic System (FLS) consists of five main parts: (1) fuzzifier; (2) membership function; (3) rules; (4) inference engine; and (5) defuzzifier.

Crisp input variables: We define five input variables (i.e., $d_{m,n,k}^w$, $c_{m,n,k}^w$, ρ_m , ρ_R , ρ_E) based on the nature of the problem to use fuzzy logic to make offloading decisions:

$$\Omega = \{d_{m,n,k}^w, c_{m,n,k}^w, \rho_m, \rho_R, \rho_E\}, \Omega \in Y^t \quad (8)$$

where $d_{m,n,k}^w$ and $c_{m,n,k}^w$ are the weighted data size and weighted NRCC. ρ_m , ρ_R , and ρ_E are the utilization coefficients of the SMD, wireless channel, and edge node, respectively. The values of these variables are calculated as described in [9].

Linguistic variables: The linguistic variables of input $\{d_{m,n,k}^w, c_{m,n,k}^w\}$ are described as large/big, medium, and small, and the variables of input $\{\rho_m, \rho_R, \rho_E\}$ are described as low, medium, and high. The linguistic variables are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Fuzzification input variables

Fuzzification	Variables	Fuzzy Set	Membership Function	Ranges
Weighted DS	$d_{m,n,k}^w$	Large	L-R open shoulder	0 - 0.4
		Medium	Triangular	0.3 - 0.7
		Small	L-R open shoulder	0.6 - 1.0
Weighted NRCC	$c_{m,n,k}^w$	Large	L-R open shoulder	0 - 0.4
		Medium	Triangular	0.3 - 0.7
		Small	L-R open shoulder	0.6 - 1.0
SMD Utilization	ρ_m	Low	L-R open shoulder	0 - 60
		Medium	Triangular	35 - 85
		High	L-R open shoulder	80 - 100
Wireless Channel Utilization	ρ_R	Low	L-R open shoulder	0 - 60
		Medium	Triangular	35 - 85
		High	L-R open shoulder	80 - 100
Edge node Utilization	ρ_E	Low	L-R open shoulder	0 - 60
		Medium	Triangular	35 - 85
		High	L-R open shoulder	80 - 100

Membership functions: In our model, we use three membership functions: triangular, left-right open shoulder, and generalized bell-shaped. We associate a grade with each linguistic term, and the crisp value is transformed into a fuzzy value in the fuzzification step by using the following membership functions. Membership functions (MF) can be defined mathematically by using $\zeta_A(\chi): \chi \rightarrow [0,1], \forall \chi \in X$, where each element of χ is within the range of 0 and 1.

A is the fuzzy set which is described using $A = \{(\chi, \zeta_A(\chi)) : \chi \in X\}$.

$$\zeta_A^{\text{triangular}}(\chi) = \begin{cases} 0; & \text{if } \chi \leq p \\ \frac{\chi-p}{h-p}; & \text{if } p < \chi \leq h \\ \frac{q-\chi}{q-h}; & \text{if } h < \chi \leq q \\ 0; & \text{if } \chi \geq q \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\zeta_A^{\text{left}}(\chi) = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if } \chi \leq p \\ \frac{q-\chi}{q-p}; & \text{if } p < \chi \leq q \\ 0; & \text{if } \chi \geq q \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\zeta_A^{\text{right}}(\chi) = \begin{cases} 0; & \text{if } \chi \leq p \\ \frac{\chi-p}{q-p}; & \text{if } p < \chi \leq q \\ 1; & \text{if } \chi \geq q \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\zeta_A^{\text{gbell}}(\chi) = \frac{1}{1 + \left| \frac{\chi-c}{a} \right|^{2b}} \quad (12)$$

A generalized bell-shaped membership function depends on three parameters a, b, c . Where χ input values, a and b control the width of the function, and c controls the center of the function.

The fuzzifier defines fuzzy classes for each fuzzy variable as follows [6]:

$$F_{d_{m,n,k}^w}(\chi) = [\mu_{d_{m,n,k}^w}^S(\chi), \mu_{d_{m,n,k}^w}^M(\chi), \mu_{d_{m,n,k}^w}^L(\chi)] \quad (13)$$

$$F_{c_{m,n,k}^w}(\chi) = [\mu_{c_{m,n,k}^w}^S(\chi), \mu_{c_{m,n,k}^w}^M(\chi), \mu_{c_{m,n,k}^w}^B(\chi)] \quad (14)$$

$$F_{\rho_m}(\chi) = [\mu_{\rho_m}^L(\chi), \mu_{\rho_m}^M(\chi), \mu_{\rho_m}^H(\chi)] \quad (15)$$

$$F_{\rho_R}(\chi) = [\mu_{\rho_R}^L(\chi), \mu_{\rho_R}^M(\chi), \mu_{\rho_R}^H(\chi)] \quad (16)$$

$$F_{\rho_E}(\chi) = [\mu_{\rho_E}^L(\chi), \mu_{\rho_E}^M(\chi), \mu_{\rho_E}^H(\chi)] \quad (17)$$

Fuzzy values are calculated using membership functions of the fuzzifier, which are depicted in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Membership functions of input variables.

Fuzzy rules: The fuzzy rule set is created using the straightforward IF-AND-THEN rule. We find experimentally fuzzy rule sets and change them to determine the fuzzy rules. Among the different fuzzy rule sets, we chose the best rule combination in the computational experiments. The number of fuzzy rules is $n = 3^5 = 243$ based on five membership functions with three linguistic terms. A fuzzy logic system with a large number of rules takes a long time to make offloading decisions. To avoid it, we chose a small number of fuzzy rules based on expert opinions in this field. Those rules are enough to make offloading decisions for heavy subtasks. The remaining subtasks, which are not in the range of the fuzzy rules, get offloaded in the next step using the NSGA-III algorithm.

Table 3: Fuzzy Logic rules

Rule #	DS	NRCC	SMD utilization	Wireless channel utilization	MEC node utilization	Decision
R1	Large	Small	Low	High	Low	Local
R2	Large	Small	Low	Low	High	Local
R3	Large	Medium	Low	High	High	Local
R4	Small	Big	Medium	Low	Low	MEC
R5	Small	Big	High	Medium	Low	MEC
R6	Small	Big	High	Low	Medium	MEC
R7	Medium	Big	High	Low	Low	MEC

Defuzzification: Defuzzification consists of drawing the output deterministic value from the fuzzy model. A careful analysis of the problem is the foundation of correct defuzzification: it can be linguistic, when the output is a predicate with a level of membership associated, or numerical, when the output is of non-fuzzy types ("crisp"). The most used defuzzification methods are the centroid method, the bisector method, the middle of maximum, the largest of maximum, and the smallest of maximum. The centroid defuzzifier method is the most widely used, which returns the center of gravity (*COG*) of the aggregated fuzzy set. In this work, we use the centroid method for the defuzzification step. An example of a calculation of the value of *COG* is presented in Fig. 3. The value of *COG* is calculated as follows

$$COG(\text{Execution}), \quad \chi^* = \frac{\int \chi \zeta(\chi) d\chi}{\int \zeta(\chi) d\chi} \quad (18)$$

Table 4: Fuzzification of output

Offloading Decision	Membership Function	Ranges
Local Execution	Generalized Bell-Shaped	0 – 50
NSGA	Generalized Bell-Shaped	15 – 85
MEC	Generalized Bell-Shaped	50 – 100

Figure 3: Output membership function and COG for offloading decision.

Algorithm 1: Fuzzy logic-based computation offloading algorithm

Result: Offloading decisions

Initialization:

Set of SMDs $\mathcal{M} = \{U_1, U_2, U_3, \dots, U_M\}$

Set of tasks $\mathcal{N} = \{\tau_{m,1}, \tau_{m,2}, \tau_{m,3}, \dots, \tau_{m,N}\}$

$\mathcal{A} = \emptyset$

COG \leftarrow 0 **foreach** SMD $U_m \in \mathcal{M}$ **do**

foreach subtask $\tau_{m,n,k} \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**

 1: Calculate the values of $d_{m,n,k}^w, c_{m,n,k}^w,$

$\rho_m, \rho_R,$ and ρ_E

 2: $COG =$

FuzzyLogic($d_{m,n,k}^w, c_{m,n,k}^w, \rho_m, \rho_R, \rho_E$)

if $COG < 30$ **then**

$x_{m,n,k} = 0$

else

$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A} \cup \{\tau_{m,n}\}$

end

if $COG > 70$ **then**

$x_{m,n,k} = 1$

else

$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A} \cup \{\tau_{m,n}\}$

end

end

end

The NSGA-III algorithm-based offloading decisions. For undefined subtasks via Algorithm 1, offloading decisions are made using the NSGA-III

algorithm with some changes. In this work, we describe only the modifications according to the **P1**. The problem requires meeting the deadline. To achieve this objective, each solution is assessed, among other constraints, to ensure that the completion time does not exceed the deadline. Thus, the NSGA-III algorithm evaluates the solutions as follows:

Evaluate the solutions: We calculate the objective functions using Eqs. (1), (2), and (7). Constraints in (8) are defined as constraint violation (CV) as follows:

$$CV_{m,n}^1 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } T_{m,n,k_n} \leq \theta_{m,n} \\ T_{m,n,k_n} - \theta_{m,n}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$CV_{m,n,k}^2 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } T_{m,n,k} \geq T_{m,n,z} \\ T_{m,n,k} - T_{m,n,z}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$CV = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N (CV_{m,n}^1 + \sum_{k=1}^{k_n} CV_{m,n,k}^2) \quad (22)$$

The chromosomes that satisfy constraints in (8) are feasible solutions. According to the values of objective functions and CV, the fittest chromosomes are selected in the next step. Other parts of the algorithm work the same as described in [9].

The proposed hybrid method. The hybrid CO method works as follows: A set of tasks from all SMDs and parameters of the algorithms are given. One task from each SMD is selected. The initial population size and number of iterations are defined by the initial population size and selected tasks. By decreasing the number of tasks, the initial population size and number of iterations also decrease. We set these parameters to at least 10 in the case of a minimum number of tasks. First, a fuzzy logic-based algorithm is used to find offloading decisions based on preferences. The preferences are based on expert opinions. The subtasks that do not satisfy the fuzzy rules are left for further finding the optimal solution. Next, the NSGA-III-based algorithm generates its initial population considering the offloading decisions made by Algorithm 1. It finds offloading decisions for the remaining subtasks. The tasks that get offloading decisions are removed from the set of tasks. Thus, our proposed method uses the strengths of two algorithms to make more rational offloading decisions. The process is given in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: The algorithm of the proposed hybrid method

Result: Offloading decisions

Initialization:

Set of tasks \mathcal{N} from \mathcal{M} number of SMDs;

P_i, I_i

while $\mathcal{N} \neq \emptyset$ **do**

 Select a task from each SMD;

$N_s \leftarrow$ number of selected tasks;

$\zeta = N_s/N$;

$P = \lfloor \zeta \cdot P_i + 10 \rfloor$;

$I = \lfloor \zeta \cdot I_i + 10 \rfloor$;

 Making offloading decisions using Algorithm 1;

 Making offloading decisions using Algorithm 3 in [9];

 Remove tasks N_s ;

end

Experimental Results. Experiments are conducted using simulations on MATLAB 2024b. The simulation environment is the same as described in [9]. In this section, we analyze our system with varied values of DS and NRCC. At the beginning of each experiment, we generate a random data set. It consists of information that describes tasks, SMDs, wireless channels, and edge nodes. To generate the data set, we give initial information, such as the computation power of the MEC node and the number of small cells connected to the MeNB. A random number of SMDs can be placed in each small cell. For each SMD, the arrival rate of tasks, the values of transmission power, and the computation power of the SMD are assigned randomly. It means that the specifications of SMDs differ. Then, the number of subtasks in each task is chosen in the range of 6–12. Each subtask is given by two parameters, DS and NRCC, whose values are generated by a given average value following the exponential distribution.

The experiment is repeated 100 times. The statistical results of a set of experiments are given by the box plot. The experiments aim to compare the behaviour of existing (Random offloading and Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MOPSO)-

based) offloading methods and the proposed method under varying workloads.

Figure 4: Impact of DS on latency and energy consumption in different methods.

First, the impacts of increasing DS on offloading methods such as the random offloading method, the MOPSO algorithm-based method, and our proposed method were studied. The effects of increasing DS on average latency and energy consumption are depicted as a comparison of the three methods in Fig. 4. The random offloading method performs the worst in terms of minimizing latency and energy consumption. The MOPSO-based method outperformed the random offloading method. The proposed method outperformed both methods in all DS-increasing cases.

Figure 5: Impact of DS on the probability of task failure and deadline violation in different methods.

The impacts of increasing DS on offloading methods in terms of probability of task failure and average value of deadline violation are shown in Fig. 5. In this case, the random offloading method significantly reduced the probability of task failure. The MOPSO-based method was the worst case in all sets of experiments. The proposed hybrid method gave the best result in the set of experiments. Overall, considering our multiobjective optimization problem, the proposed method has shown significantly better results. Also, we added the average deadline violation to our comparison. From this point of view, the proposed hybrid method has also produced the best results in four sets of experiments.

Figure 6: Impact of NRCC on latency and energy consumption in different methods.

The following experiments were conducted to determine how increasing NRCC affected offloading methods. An increasing NRCC creates a bigger workload on the CPU of the SMD or MEC node. As a result, the values of objective functions emerge theoretically. We can see it in the results of almost all sets of experiments in Figs. 6 and 7. In some cases, random offloading yields better results, and vice versa. But in all of the experiments, the proposed hybrid method did better than the random offloading and MOPSO-based methods.

Figure 7: Impact of NRCC on the probability of task failure and DV in different methods.

Conclusion

This work aims to design a hybrid computation offloading method using fuzzy logic and the NSGA-III algorithm for MEC-enabled SMD devices. The problem is to minimize the latency, energy consumption, and probability of task failure of dependent and deadline-constrained tasks for resource-limited MEC systems. Solving the problem leads to improving the QoS of services for latency-sensitive applications.

The proposed method was evaluated against existing methods and demonstrated improved performance in terms of latency, energy consumption, and deadline satisfaction.

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